

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

GB_SynP: a modular dCas9-regulated synthetic promoter collection for fine-tuned recombinant gene expression in plants.

Elena Moreno-Giménez¹, Sara Selma¹, Camilo Calvache¹, and Diego Orzáez^{1*}.

¹Instituto Biología Molecular y celular de Plantas, CSIC-UPV, Valencia, Spain

*Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to dorzaez@ibmcp.upv.es

Table S1. Sequences of the A3 minimal promoters designed in this study for the GB_SynP collection. Highlighted in bold are the predicted TATA boxes of each promoter sequence. Underlined sequences corresponds to predicted 5' UTR regions.

GB CODE	PART NAME	ORGANISM	SEQUENCE (TATA BOX IN BOLD, 5' UTR UNDERLINED)
GB3408	mCHS	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	atctctagctaccattcttttctttggacttcata tataaa tatatagttcacaacccc <u>ccatgcaacaaaaat</u> <u>acaccaagacaattatcactctttcattcacgtagtcctaaacacaaaaaacctagcatatccaccatttttcc</u> <u>ggcgaaa</u>
GB3409	mANS	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	tatcttgatgagataaattcaagtgct tataa atacctaacgaaaagttatagttagcag <u>tactgaaaaaa</u> <u>cgagataaac</u>
GB3410	mTA29	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	tttgcagttgtgtgatgtctgtct tata tatgcccttggtgcaagtgtaacag <u>tacaacatcatcactc</u> <u>aatcaagtttttacttaagaaattagctaaa</u>
GB3412	mPCPS2	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	tttaattttgcccttcatcaagaggcaatata taaa taagcctgcgccattgcaacaactcaaacatttccaat <u>attgctcacaagtcagtagtccttctctcaaacgttcattgtctttatctctcccaattctcattggaa</u> <u>gaataaaacaaaaattaattagaa</u>
GB3411	m2S3	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	gcatgcatgattcttacagtgattgccatgcaaatctcttctcac tataa atacaaaccaacccttacta cactcttca ctcaaac caaaaacagaaaacatacaaaatagcaaac
GB3413	mPAF	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>	tgtcacctttcacacagagctcatgattgttt tataa aggcgcttcatgaccctcaattccatagatcactc <u>ccatcacagcatttcgatatcttcaaccactttaaccttctccagaggatcatcatctcaagccctcata</u>
GB3414	mGPDA	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	tttgtgccat ttt ctgctctccccaccagctgctcttttcttcttcttccatctcagtatattcatctt <u>ccatccaagaaccttaa</u>

Table S2. Summary of all DNA parts included to date in the GB_SynP collection.

	GB_SynP A1 parts (distal promoters)			GB_SynP A2 parts (proximal promoters)		GB_SynP A3 parts (minimal promoters)
	1x target for gRNA1	2x target for gRNA1	3x target for gRNA1	1 target for gRNA2	1 target for gRNA3	
R1	G1aG2b.1	G1ab.1	G1abc.1	G1aG2b.1	G3aG2b.1	mDFR
R2	G1aG2b.2	G1ab.2	G1abc.2	G1aG2b.2		mANS
R3	G1aG2b.3	G1ab.3	G1abc.3	G1aG2b.3		mCHS
	G1aG2b.4	G1ab.4	G1abc.4	G1aG2b.4		mPCPS2
	G1aG2b.5	G1ab.5	G1abc.5	G1aG2b.5		mTA29
	G1aG2b.6			G1aG2b.6		m2S3
	G1aG2b.7			G1aG2b.7		mPAF
	G1dG2b.1			G1dG2b.1		mGPDA
	G1b.1					
	G1e.1					

Table S3. DNA parts and assemblies created and/or used in this study.

GB Code	Part Name	Description
GB1119	pEGB 35s:Luciferase:TNos-SF-35s:Renilla:TNos-35s:P19:TNos	Module for the expression of the Firefly luciferase, the Renilla luciferase and the P19 silencing suppressor genes driven by the 35s promoter and the nos terminator.
GB1160	pEGB SIDFR:Luc:TNos-SF-35s:Renilla:TNos-35s:P19:TNos	Module for the expression of the Firefly luciferase gene driven by the <i>S.lycopersicum</i> DFR promoter and terminator, the Renilla luciferase gene and the silencing suppressor P19 driven by the 35s promoter and the Nos terminator.
GB1190	pEGB 35s:dCas9-EDLL:tNOS	TU for the expression of the dCas9 with the activation domain EDLL as a CT fusion.
GB1398	pEGB3alpha2 Pnos:luc:TNos-SF-35S:Ren:TNos-35s:P19:TNos-SF	Module for the expression of the Firefly Luciferase under the regulation of the Nos promoter, and the Renilla Luciferase and the P19 silencing suppressor under the regulation of the 35S promoter.
GB1603	35s:dCas9-SunTag:TNos	TU for the expression of the dCas9 fused to the SunTag epitope.
GB1738	Alpha2: 35s_MS2:EDLL_Tnos	TU for the constitutive expression of the MS2 coat protein fused on Ct to the activation domain EDLL.
GB1824	Alpha2_35s-dCas9:ERF2-Tnos	TU for the constitutive expression of dCas9 fused to the transcriptional activation domain ERF2.
GB1833	Alpha2_35s-MS2:ERF2-Tnos	TU for the constitutive expression of the MS2 coat protein fused on Ct to the transactivation domain of ERF2.
GB1867	Alpha2_35s-ScFv:VPR-Tnos	TU for constitutive expression of ScFv antibody fused to VPR activation.
GB1869	Alpha2_35s-ScFv:ERF2-Tnos	TU for constitutive expression of ScFv antibody fused to ERF2 activation domain.
GB2085	Omega1_35s-Ms2:VPR-Tnos-35s-dCas9:EDLL-Tnos	Module for the expression of Ms2 protein fused to VPR and dCas9 fused to EDLL.
GB2034	Alpha1: 2gRNA SIDFR	Multiplex construct to target SIDFR in -150 position.
GB2035	Alpha1: 3gRNA SIDFR	Multiplex construct to target SIDFR in +31 position.
GB2036	Alpha1: 4gRNA SIDFR	Multiplex construct to target SIDFR in -1320 position.
GB2037	Alpha1:5gRNA SIDFR	Multiplex construct to target SIDFR in -1052 position.
GB2038	Alpha1:6gRNA SIDFR	Multiplex construct to target SIDFR in -979 position.
GB2039	Alpha1:7gRNA SIDFR	Multiplex construct to target SIDFR in -683 position.
GB2566	pUPD2_miniDFR	Minimal promoter of SIDFR gene containing 62bp upstream the transcription start site and the 5'UTR region.
GB2815	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A1) Random Sequence R1	Random sequence R1 of 1240 bp for A1 distal promoter position.
GB2878	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1aG2b.1	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequences for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB2879	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1aG2b.5	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequences for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB2880	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1aG2b.6	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequences for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB2881	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1aG2b.2	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequences for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB2882	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1aG2b.3	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequences for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB2883	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1aG2b.4	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequences for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB2884	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1ab.2	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of two times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB2885	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1ab.1	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of two times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.

GB2886	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1ab.3	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of two times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB2887	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1ab.6	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of two times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB2888	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1ab.4	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of two times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB2889	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1ab.5	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of two times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB2890	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1dG2b.1	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1, at "d site" positioned at -120 from TSS) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB2891	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1abc.1	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of three times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB2894	Alpha1_R1:G1aG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB2895	Alpha1_R1:G1aG2b.5:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB2896	Alpha1_R1:G1aG2b.6:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB2897	Alpha1_R1:G1aG2b.2:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB2898	Alpha1_R1:G1aG2b.3:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB2899	Alpha1_R1:G1aG2b.4:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB2900	Alpha1_R1:G1ab.2:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing the target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) twice.
GB2901	Alpha1_R1:G1ab.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing the target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) twice.
GB2902	Alpha1_R1:G1ab.3:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing the target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) twice.
GB2904	Alpha1_R1:G1ab.4:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing the target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) twice.
GB2905	Alpha1_R1:G1ab.5:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing the target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) twice.
GB2906	Alpha1_R1:G1dG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1, at "d site") and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB2907	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB2909	Omega1_R1:G1aG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2910	Omega1_R1:G1aG2b.5:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2912	Omega1_R1:G1aG2b.2:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target

		for gRNA1 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2913	Omega1_R1:G1aG2b.3:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2914	Omega1_R1:G1aG2b.4:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2915	Omega1_R1:G1ab.2:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with the target for gRNA1 twice, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2916	Omega1_R1:G1ab.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with the target for gRNA1 twice, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2917	Omega1_R1:G1ab.3:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with the target for gRNA1 twice, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2919	Omega1_R1:G1ab.4:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with the target for gRNA1 twice, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2920	Omega1_R1:G1ab.5:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with the target for gRNA1 twice, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2921	Omega1_R1:G1dG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 (d site) and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB2922	Omega1_R1:G1abc.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3269	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A1) Random Sequence R2	Random sequence R2 of 1240 bp for A1 distal promoter position.
GB3270	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A1) Random Sequence R3	Random sequence R3 of 1240 bp for A1 distal promoter position.
GB3271	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1aG2b.7	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB3272	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1b.1	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) at "b site" (-210 from TSS).
GB3273	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1e.1	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) at "e site" (-320 from TSS).
GB3274	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G3aG2b.1	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of the target sequences for the gRNA-4 NOS (gRNA3) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2) flanked by random sequences.
GB3275	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1abc.2	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of three times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB3276	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1abc.3	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of three times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB3277	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1abc.4	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of three times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB3278	pUPD2_GB_SynP (A2) G1abc.5	A2 Proximal promoter sequence consisting of three times the target sequence for the gRNA-1 DFR (gRNA1) flanked by random sequences.
GB3279	Alpha1_R2:G1aG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R2 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB3280	Alpha1_R2:G1ab.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R2 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing the target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) twice.
GB3281	Alpha1_R2:G1abc:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R2 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.

GB3282	Alpha1_R3:G1aG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R3 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB3283	Alpha1_R3:G1ab.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R3 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing the target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) twice.
GB3284	Alpha1_R3:G1abc:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R3 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3285	Omega1_R2:G1aG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R2, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3286	Omega1_R2:G1ab.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R2, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with the target for gRNA1 twice, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3287	Omega1_R2:G1abc:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R2, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3288	Omega1_R3:G1aG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R3, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3289	Omega1_R3:G1ab.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R3, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with the target for gRNA1 twice, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3290	Omega1_R3:G1abc:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R3, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3317	Alpha1_R1:G1aG2b.7:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB3318	Alpha1_R1:G1b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1, at "b site").
GB3319	Alpha1_R1:G1e.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1, at "e site").
GB3320	Alpha1_R1:G3aG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR parts, and an A2 part containing a target for the gRNA-4 NOS (gRNA3) and gRNA-5 DFR (gRNA2).
GB3321	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.2:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the gRNA1-DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3322	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.3:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the gRNA1-DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3323	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.4:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the gRNA1-DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3324	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.5:mDFR:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the gRNA1-DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3325	Omega1_R1:G1aG2b.7:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3326	Omega1_R1:G1b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 (b site) and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3327	Omega1_R1:G1e.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA1 (e site) and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.

GB3328	Omega1_R1:G3aG2b.1:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part containing a target for gRNA3 and gRNA2, and for the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3329	Omega1_R1:G1abc.2:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3330	Omega1_R1:G1abc.3:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3331	Omega1_R1:G1abc.4:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3332	Omega1_R1:G1abc.5:mDFR:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIDFR, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3408	pUPD2_mSICHS	Minimal promoter of sICHS1 gene (Solyc09g091510) containing 62bp upstream the transcription start site and the 5'UTR region.
GB3409	pUPD2_mSIANS	Minimal promoter of sIANS gene (Solyc10g076660) containing 62bp upstream the transcription start site and the 5'UTR region.
GB3410	pUPD2_mNtTA29	Minimal promoter of NtTA29 gene containing 62bp upstream the transcription start site and the 5'UTR region (from GB1477 sequence).
GB3411	pUPD2_mAt2S3	Minimal promoter of At2S3 gene containing 84bp upstream the transcription start site and the 5'UTR region (from GB0029 sequence).
GB3412	pUPD2_mNtPCPS2	Minimal promoter of NtPCPS2 gene containing 62bp upstream the transcription start site and the 5'UTR region (from GB1027 sequence).
GB3413	pUPD2_mPcPAF	Minimal promoter of PcPAF gene containing 62bp upstream the transcription start site and the 5'UTR region (from FB029 sequence).
GB3414	pUPD2_mAnGPDA	Minimal promoter of AnGPDA gene containing 62bp upstream the transcription start site and the 5'UTR region (from FB007 sequence).
GB3520	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:mSICHS:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1 and A3 mSICS parts, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3521	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:mSIANS:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIANS, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3522	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:mNtTA29:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mNtTA29, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3523	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:mAt2S3:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mAt2S3, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3524	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:mNtPCPS2:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mNtPCPS2, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3525	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:mPcPAF:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mPcPAF, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3526	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:mAnGPDA:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mAnGPDA, and an A2 part containing three times the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) target sequence.
GB3527	Omega1_R1:G1abc.1:mSICHS:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSICHS, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3528	Omega1_R1:G1abc.1:mSIANS:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mSIANS, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3529	Omega1_R1:G1abc.1:mNtTA29:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mNtTA29, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.

GB3530	Omega1_R1:G1abc.1:mAt2S3:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mAt2S3, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3531	Omega1_R1:G1abc.1:mNtPCPS2:luc: t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mNtPCPS2, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3532	Omega1_R1:G1abc.1:mPcPAF:luc: t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mPcPAF, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB3533	Omega1_R1:G1abc.1:mAnGPDA:luc: t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R1, A3 mAnGPDA, and an A2 part with three times the target for gRNA1, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB4435	Alpha1_R2:G1ab.1:min2S3:luc:t35s	TU for the expression of firefly luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R2 and A3 mAt2S3 parts, and an A2 part containing the target for the gRNA-1DFR (gRNA1) twice.
GB4436	Omega1_R2:G1ab.1:min2S3:luc:t35s +P19(TU) +Renilla(TU)	Module for the expression of luciferase driven by a GB_SynP promoter with A1 R2, A3 mAt2S3, and an A2 part with the target for gRNA1 twice, and the constitutive expression of renilla and P19.
GB4437	Alpha1_p35s:HisP5:t35s	TU for constitutive expression of HisP5 enzyme
GB4438	Alpha1_p35s:Luz:t35s	TU for constitutive expression of Luz enzyme
GB4439	Alpha2_p35s:H3H:t35s	TU for constitutive expression of H3H enzyme
GB4440	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:minPCPS2:HisP5:t35s	TU for inducible expression of HisP5 enzyme, using a GB_SynP promoter with one copy of the target sequence for gRNA1 (1x).
GB4441	Alpha1_R1:G1abc.1:minPCPS2:Luz:t35s	TU for inducible expression of Luz enzyme, using a dCasEV-regulated synthetic promoter with one copy of the target sequence for gRNA1DFR (1x).
GB4442	Alpha2_R1:G1abc.1:minPCPS2:H3H:t35s	TU for inducible expression of H3H enzyme, using a dCasEV-regulated synthetic promoter with one copy of the target sequence for gRNA1DFR (1x).
GB4443	Alpha1_R2:G1ab.1:min2S3:HisP5:t35s	TU for inducible expression of HisP5 enzyme, using a dCasEV-regulated synthetic promoter with two copies of the target sequence for gRNA1DFR (2x).
GB4444	Alpha1_R2:G1ab.1:min2S3:Luz:t35s	TU for inducible expression of Luz enzyme, using a dCasEV-regulated synthetic promoter with two copies of the target sequence for gRNA1DFR (2x).
GB4445	Alpha2_R2:G1ab.1:min2S3:H3H:t35s	TU for inducible expression of H3H enzyme, using a dCasEV-regulated synthetic promoter with two copies of the target sequence for gRNA1DFR (2x).
GB4446	Alpha1_R3:G1aG2b.1:minDFR:HisP5:t35s	TU for inducible expression of HisP5 enzyme, using a dCasEV-regulated synthetic promoter with three copies of the target sequence for gRNA1DFR (3x).
GB4447	Alpha1_R3:G1aG2b.1:minDFR:Luz:t35s	TU for inducible expression of Luz enzyme, using a dCasEV-regulated synthetic promoter with three copies of the target sequence for gRNA1DFR (3x).
GB4448	Alpha2_R3:G1aG2b.1:minDFR:H3H:t35s	TU for inducible expression of H3H enzyme, using a dCasEV-regulated synthetic promoter with three copies of the target sequence for gRNA1DFR (3x).
GB4449	Omega1_35s:Luz:t35s+35s:H3H:t35s	Module for the constitutive expression of Luz and H3H enzymes
GB4450	Omega2_35s:HisP5:t35s+35s:CPH:tNOS	Module for the constitutive expression of HisP5 and CPH enzymes
GB4451	Omega1_1x:Luz+1x:H3H	Module for the inducible expression of (1x)Luz and (1x)H3H enzymes
GB4452	Omega1_1x:Luz+2x:H3H	Module for the inducible expression of (1x)Luz and (2x)H3H enzymes
GB4453	Omega1_1x:Luz+3x:H3H	Module for the inducible expression of (1x)Luz and (3x)H3H enzymes
GB4454	Omega1_2x:Luz+1x:H3H	Module for the inducible expression of (2x)Luz and (1x)H3H enzymes
GB4455	Omega1_2x:Luz+2x:H3H	Module for the inducible expression of (2x)Luz and (2x)H3H enzymes
GB4456	Omega1_2x:Luz+3x:H3H	Module for the inducible expression of (2x)Luz and (3x)H3H enzymes
GB4457	Omega1_3x:Luz+1x:H3H	Module for the inducible expression of (3x)Luz and (1x)H3H enzymes

A

```

G1ab.5 --CCATCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCatcgaattcgtccgtgttcattgtatatatgcaca 58
G1ab.4 --CCATCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCaagaccagggggctcgccggttggctaactcctg 58
G1ab.1 -tCCCTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCagtcgtgaaagtcatagtaccctgggtaccaactt 59
G1abc.4 -tCCCTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCacgaccgcttcacgctaaagtgctggccacgctc 59
G1abc.3 -tCCCTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCagttgggttcaccgggctcggacctgagtcgacca 59
G1abc.1 -tCCCTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCgtatatacctgtttcaattcgtttttctcgtctacag 59
G1abc.2 -tCCCTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCaagcggcggctaccgagtcgtaacaagtcgagtcag 59
G1abc.5 -tCCCTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCcttactgtatgagtagtaatttctcgcgagatgtcg 59
G1a.4 -GCTGTATCTAATAGAATCTTCGGGcgtacatctacctgaggtctgtggcccgtgg 58
G1a.6 --GCTGTATCTAATAGAATCTTCGGGcgtacatctacctgaggtctgtggcccgtgg 58
G1ab.3 taCCATCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCcttgaattcgcgagactcagtaagacacgggtctagc 60
G1a.5 ---CTGTATCTAATAGAATCTTCGGGtgaattcattactgtcctaaccgctcagttcgt 57
G1a.2 --GCTGTATCTAATAGAATCTTAGGGgaaattcagatctacctcctaaggcactacgaag 58
G1ab.2 --CCATCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCagtgagctcctgtgctcggtggctatttggatagg 58
G1a.1 --GCTGTATCTAATAGAATCTTCGGGacatggggcgtttggcactaccgacacgaacctcag 58
G1a.3 -aGCTGTATCTAATAGAATCTTAGGacatggggcgtttggcactaccgacacgaacctcag 59
      *      *      *      *      *
G1ab.5 agCCGTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCaagcaggctaggatataatgtcgaagcccttcccca 118
G1ab.4 gtCCCTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTcacatcttgaatgaattcagtagaaaaatttgtg 118
G1ab.1 accCGTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCcgtggttctcgtgggtgagctcgagactcgtgggga 119
G1abc.4 aaCCGTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTctggcgttgaatgagtcgactctatagCCATCTTC 119
G1abc.3 agCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCgagcggcagaaactacgctcaggggtCCGTCTTC 119
G1abc.1 cccCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCacctgcaactacctactgctgggtccgcaCCGTCTTC 119
G1abc.2 gcCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCcaatcccagggctcagccgacatataCCATCTTC 119
G1abc.5 gtCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCtaacgctcgtatctacgtcagcagcagCCGTCTTC 119
G1a.4 caCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCggagcgttaactcagcggctatccagcaacactacgct 118
G1a.6 gtCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCgagcggctcgtgactgctactcttcgcaagaat 118
G1ab.3 tgCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCggagtcgggtgtgagcgaagaatcaaggcagcccta 120
G1a.5 cgCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCgattcctgctgaataaacaactctgtagccaagcaa- 116
G1a.2 gaCCATCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCcaggggctcagatccaggctgggattttgacatg 118
G1ab.2 tcCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCtctatcactggaatcggacgctgaggtaggat--- 115
G1a.1 ttCCTTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCagaacactggaaatgggacgctgaggtaggat--- 115
G1a.3 ttCCGTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTctcgccagagctcgtcagcatactcgaagaat--- 116
      ** *****
G1ab.5 agcgttcagggtgggatttgcataacttccga----- 151
G1ab.4 ttagaaggcagagtcaccatgtacaaaagcga----- 151
G1ab.1 cagctcttcatacatagagcggcggcgtcgaac----- 152
G1abc.4 TCTACCAACCAGTCcagggcggctcgtt----- 148
G1abc.3 TCTACCAACCAGTCtcccgggtatctc----- 148
G1abc.1 TCTACCAACCAGTCccaggaggacctc----- 148
G1abc.2 TCTACCAACCAGTCgtagctaaactatgt----- 148
G1abc.5 TCTACCAACCAGTCagggctagaattac----- 148
G1a.4 a----tctggtcatatcataagattccgagcagctcaa--- 151
G1a.6 g----gtggtccagcggctcgaactcagctcaacatag-- 151
G1ab.3 ggtagcaaccgcccggcttcggcggttaag---ggaat-- 153
G1a.5 ----gacttcggcgtccttgggtggggacgctatgaat-- 150
G1a.2 gagaggctggtaattgttttgggtggtgctgaat----- 151
G1ab.2 ----ggcttgcctttcattcgttggcagactgagctctta 151
G1a.1 ----cggttgtcctatcttctggtgcccagactgagcagaat 151
G1a.3 ----caaggcaggtcaattcgcactgtgagagtcgaagt 152

```

B

```

G1d.1 ----- 0
G1a.7 ----- 0
G3aG2b.1 ----- 0
G1b.1 ----- 0
G1e.1 CCGTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTCatactggagctgtaccggtattgctgcatagatg 60
G1d.1 ----- 0
G1a.7 ----- 0
G3aG2b.1 ----- 0
G1b.1 ----- CATTTCTC 9
G1e.1 cagtgctgctcttatcacatttgtttcgacgacagcgccttcgcagtttccctcagacac 120
G1d.1 -----taGCTGTATCTAATAGAAT 19
G1a.7 -----GCTGTATCTAATAGAATCTTCGGcattagtggtgctggcgaataat 47
G3aG2b.1 -----GCTGTATCTAATAGAATCTTCGGcattagtggtgctggcgaataat 47
G1b.1 TCACCAACCAGTCccttattgtaggcagagggcagccttattagtggtgctggcgaataat 69
G1e.1 ttaagaataagcgtctattgtaggcagagggcagccttattagtggtgctggcgaataat 180
      *      *      *      *
G1d.1 CTTGgagcgaattcctgtgctcgggtggtcaaatggatcgtgCCGTCTTCTCTACCAA 79
G1a.7 cttctaagcgaatCCGTCTTCTCTACCAACCAGTctcctgtgctcgggtggtcaaatgg 107
G3aG2b.1 cttctaagcgaatCCAGAAACCCGGCTCAGTGGctcctgtgctcgggtggtcaaatgg 107
G1b.1 c-----ttctaagcgaattcctgtgctcgggtggtcaaatgg 106
G1e.1 c-----ttctaagcgaattcctgtgctcgggtggtcaaatgg 217
      *      *      *      *
G1d.1 CCAGTCgctgctgaatcagccgtatccagcaacactacgctatc 123
G1a.7 atcgtggctgctgaatcagccgtatccagcaacactacgctatc 151
G3aG2b.1 atcgtggctgctgaatcagccgtatccagcaacactacgctatc 151
G1b.1 atcgtggctgctgaatcagccgtatccagcaacactacgctatc 150
G1e.1 atcgtggctgctgaatcagccgtatccagcaacactacgctatc 261
      ** *****

```

Figure S1. Alignment of A2 parts sequences included in the GB_SynP collection. (A) Alignment of the three A2 parts series including different repetitions of the gRNA1 target (G1a.N, G1ab,N and G1abc.N). (B) Alignment of the A2 part series including the target for gRNA1 at different positions (G1d.1, G1a.7, G1b.1 and G1e.1) and the G3a.1 part that contains the same sequence as G1a.7 but replacing the gRNA1 target by gRNA3 target. Alignments were performed using CLUSTAL-Omega (v1.2.4). Capital letters denote the target sequences for the different gRNAs.

Figure S2. Expression range of the GB_SynP promoters used for regulation of LUZ pathway. Normalized (Fluc/Rluc) expression levels of *Nicotiana benthamiana* leaves transiently expressing a luciferase reporter gene (Fluc) under the regulation of promoter R3:G1a.1:mDFR (1x gRNA-target), R2:G1ab.1:m2S3 (2x gRNA-target) or R1:G1abc.1:mPCPS2 (3x gRNA-target). Luciferase under *NOS* and CaMV 35s promoters (p*NOS* and p35S, respectively) were included as references. Letters denote statistically significance between (activated) promoters in a one-way ANOVA (Tukey's multiple comparisons test, $p \leq 0.05$) performed on the log-transformed data. Error bars represent the average values \pm SD (n=3).

Figure S3. Basal expression of the Time-course experiment including the 27 constructs expressing the LUZ pathway transiently in *Nicotiana benthamiana* leaves under the regulation of 1x, 2x or 3x GB_SynP promoters. Fluorescence and luminescence signals corresponds to the co-infiltration in *Nicotiana benthamiana* leaves of each LUZ pathway construct with dCasEV2.1 and an irrelevant gRNA (gRNA3). Error bars represent the average values \pm SD (n=12).